

**PROBLEMS IN THE EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES OF CHILDREN WITH
DISABILITIES AND TYPES OF PSYCHOLOGICAL SUPPORT****Joldasbaev Mansur**

Student of Karakalpak State University

Axmetov Jamshid

Student of Karakalpak State University

Tanjarbaev Ulan

Student of Karakalpak State University

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Abstract. *This study provides information on educational problems and types of psychological support for students with disabilities in the application of modern stages of inclusive education in the education of students with disabilities. The study also provides information on the main essence and methods of inclusive education.*

Keywords: *Inclusive education, psychological research, pedagogical approaches, psychological interviewing, inclusive education methods.*

**NOGIRON BOLALAR TA'LIM FAOLIYATIDAGI MUAMMOLAR VA
PSIXOLOGIK YORDAM TURLARI**

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqotda nogironligi bo'lgan o'quvchilarni o'qitishda inklyuziv ta'limning zamonaviy bosqichlarini qo'llashda ta'limda muammolar va nogironligi mavjud bo'lgan o'quvchilarga psixologik yordam turlari haqida ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tilgan. Shuningdek tadqiqot davomida inklyuziv ta'limning asosiy mohiyati, metodlari haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Inklyuziv ta'lim, psixologik tadqiqotlar, pedagogik yondashuvlar, psixologik suhbat, inklyuziv ta'lim metodlari.*

Introduction

As is known, in inclusive education, children with special educational needs are grouped together with all children for a specific purpose according to their different abilities. While special education is carried out according to mental and physical appearance, inclusive education is determined according to the abilities and capabilities of the child. While special education is taught through special and alternative educational programs, inclusive education is taught based on a child-centered and adapted, guided, and inclusive curriculum. A particularly important aspect of inclusive education is that children and teachers learn from

each other and solve problems together. The task of inclusive education is to provide quality education to all children, regardless of their abilities and status. At the same time, the principle of inclusion implies that children with disabilities should live in families and receive education in regular schools with their peers in order to have positive mental and social development. An inclusive education system ensures that a child in a wheelchair can attend any nearby school, that if they have difficulty learning, they will receive special help to learn to read and write, and that a child who has missed classes will be provided with appropriate support to return to school. Teaching children with special needs in a general education setting requires the activities of a mobile teacher, i.e. a resource teacher. Inclusive education can be implemented in practice through the joint efforts of a mobile teacher and a regular classroom teacher. In some classes, it may be necessary to separate the child from the classroom for a certain period of time. The resource teacher should always work in conjunction with the classroom teacher and be an expert in this area of special education. The important tasks of the inter-school resource teacher include providing the necessary materials and equipment for children with disabilities, finding sponsors, involving parents in helping the school, and establishing a strong relationship between children with disabilities, healthy children, and the classroom teacher, providing assistance by providing special resource materials, advising parents, children's regular classroom teachers, and school administration, as well as holding discussions about activities and appropriate educational programs for children with special education needs, and even providing information to parents of non-disabled children. Inclusive education ensures that children with disabilities receive education on a par with their social peers, and (unless there are serious reasons for their development) they are accepted into regular schools. Children with severe disabilities are sometimes educated in special schools and special rehabilitation centers, or in special classes within regular schools using remedial programs. In these schools, educational provision is necessarily carried out taking into account the needs of the child. The regular educational process involves the use of individual correctional methods and adapted curricula, programs and other factors, in accordance with the personal characteristics of the child with disabilities, the organization of various forms of education together with the surrounding community, and the use of special aids (hearing aids, lenses, magnifying glasses, wheelchairs), various technical means and special visual aids. In turn, teachers of special educational institutions should act as local consultation departments and resource centers for general education students, parents, state and non-state community organizations. Studies on the motivation of

students with disabilities have revealed interesting things. As it turned out, the value of motivation for successful learning is higher than the student's intelligence. In cases where a student's abilities are not high enough, high positive motivation can play the role of a compensating factor, but this principle does not work in the opposite direction - no ability can compensate for the lack of motivation to learn or its low intensity and provide significant academic results. Together with the current development of modern pedagogical technologies, we can achieve good results in teaching children with disabilities. Modern educational technologies are increasingly in demand by teachers, therefore, game and communication and information technologies are used in practice. The tasks of inclusive education are: to create the necessary psychological, pedagogical and correctional conditions for the education of children and adolescents with special educational needs in an educational institution, to implement general educational programs and corrective work aimed at their capabilities, to ensure their mental development and social adaptation; to ensure equal rights of learners in education by coordinating the activities of students of special educational institutions with educational organizations; to eliminate barriers between disabled and healthy children with the active participation of society and the family, to meet the needs of the child, and to adapt them to social life early; to implement the right of disabled children and adolescents to live separately from their families; to form an alternative attitude towards children and adolescents with disabilities in society. The advantages of inclusive education are that everyone benefits from inclusive practices. Through inclusive education, children grow up to be independent and self-reliant. Their fears are reduced and they learn appropriate social skills. They also become aware of their ability to express care and compassion. Such an educational environment benefits not only the child, but also the child's parents. Because today, the first concern of a parent with a disabled child is that their child is excluded from the peer group and has difficulty learning. Now parents can freely visit the institution where their child is studying, see the environment in which their child is studying, and help. Parents benefit from joining other family members, and they expand the variety of social situations for themselves and their children.

Conclusion

They experience contact with a large group of families in their community, which reduces fears. When working with children with disabilities, the cooperation of parents, the community, and the school educational organization plays an important role in the children's educational activities and the children's learning process.

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